

HISTORICAL BALLADS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Ibragimova Dilafruz Shukhratovna
Senior Lecturer of the Department
"Practical English" FSU.

Nasrullayeva Ruhshonaxon Abdunabi qizi
Student of the Faculty
English Language and Literature FSU.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11101319>

Abstract: In this article, we will analyze English ballads and historical ballads. Also, in this article, an example of a historical ballad is given and we give information about it.

Key words: Narrative poetry, heroism, romance, betrayal, tragedy, ballad

Аннотация: В этой статье мы разберем английские баллады и исторические баллады. Также в этой статье приводится пример исторической баллады и дается информация о ней.

Ключевые слова: Повествовательная поэма, героизм, романтика, предательство, трагедия, баллада.

Izoh: Biz ushbu maqolada ingliz balladlarni va tarixiy balladani tahlil qilamiz. Shuningdek ushbu maqolada tarixiy balladaga misol keltirilgan va unga ma'lumot beramiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Hikoyaviy she'r, qahramonlik, romantika, xiyonat, tragediya, ballada.

Introduction.

The best of folk poetry were the ballads. The word "ballad" comes from the French "ballet", which in its turn was derived from the Italian word "ballare", which means, "to dance". [1, 25] A ballad is a form of narrative poetry or song that tells a story, often focusing on themes of love, loss, or adventure. Ballads typically have a simple and repetitive structure, with a strong emphasis on emotion and storytelling. Traditional ballads are often passed down orally and have been an important part of folk music and literature for centuries.

As regards to content, the ballads are usually divided into three groups: historical, heroic, and romantic ballads. Historical ballads were based on a historical fact, while heroic ballads were about people who were persecuted by the law or by their own families. [3, 57]

Historical ballads are a form of narrative poetry that tell a story about an event or figure from history. They were popular in English literature during the Middle Ages and Renaissance, often passed down orally before being written down. Historical ballads often focus on themes of heroism, romance, betrayal, and tragedy.

Historical ballads were often sung or recited at gatherings and events, serving as a way to preserve and pass down stories from the past. They continue to be studied and appreciated for their vivid storytelling and emotional impact. [5, 128]

Historical ballads typically focus on events such as battles, political intrigue, love stories, and heroic deeds. They often feature a simple rhyme scheme and refrain, making them easy to remember and recite.

The Robin Hood ballads, numbering some forty separate ballads, were written down at various times not earlier than the 14 and 15 centuries. Robin Hood is a partly historical, partly legendary character. Most probably he lived in the second half of the 12 century, during the reign of Henry II and his son Richard, the Lion Heart. The older ballads tell us much about the

Saxon yeomen, who were famous archers and keen hunters. Being ill-treated by the Norman robber-barons, they longed to live free in the forest with Robin as their leader. Robin Hood always helped the country folk in their troubles. Though sheriff put a big price on Robin's head, Saxons didn't betray him.

Thus, Robin was an outlaw and lived in Sherwood Forest. He was smart and clever "with a twinkle in the eye". Whenever the Sheriff or the king sent out a party of men to catch him, Robin fought with so much vigor that his enemies, amazed at his bravery, confessed themselves beaten and stayed with him in the forest. They became "the merry men of Robin Hood".[4, 89]

In the 16 century many new episodes were introduced into the ballads. They were arranged in series, the most popular of which was "The Jolly Life of Robin Hood and His Men in Sherwood".

In conclusion, the Robin Hood ballads are a collection of folk tales that depict the legendary figure of Robin Hood as a noble outlaw who fights against oppression and injustice. The ballads reflect a time of social unrest and inequality, with Robin Hood symbolizing the desire for freedom and justice among the common people. Despite being an outlaw, Robin Hood is portrayed as a hero who helps those in need and stands up against corrupt authorities. The stories of Robin Hood have endured through the centuries, inspiring generations with his courage, wit, and sense of justice.

References:

1. "The Ballad and the Folk" by David C. Fowler Published: 1979
2. "The Singing Tradition of Child's Popular Ballads" by Bertrand Harris Bronson Published: 1976
3. "The Ballad and Oral Literature" edited by Thomas McKean Published: 1991.
4. "The English and Scottish Popular Ballads" by Francis James Child.
5. "Ballad and History: Essays on the Ballad as Historical Narrative" edited by Patricia Fumerton and Anita Guerrini
6. "The Ballad and the Plough: A Portrait of the Life of the Old Scottish Farmtouns through the ballads of their folk poets" by David Buchan.